

Some New Constituents from Heartwood of *Aegle marmelos* Corr.

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Two new compounds, 2-(2-hydroxy-4-methoxyphenyl)vinyl acetate and xanthoxol-8-O- β -D-glucopyranoside have been isolated from the heartwood of *Aegle marmelos* along with β -sitosterol and lupeol. The structures of these compounds have been established on the basis of spectral data and chemical evidences.

AEGLE marmelos Corr. (Rutaceae) is a medicinal plant employed in Indian indigenous system of medicine^{1,2}. The literature survey reveals that no phytochemical examination has been reported on the heartwood of this plant. We report herein the isolation and characterisation of two new compounds 2-(2-hydroxy-4-methoxyphenyl)vinyl acetate (1) and xanthotoxol-8-O- β -D-glucopyranoside (3) along with β -sitosterol and lupeol on the basis of spectral data and chemical evidences.

Results and Discussion

Compound 1, C₁₁H₁₂O₄ (M⁺ 208), gave positive test with FeCl₃ and formed an acetate derivative. Its ir spectrum indicated the presence of hydroxyl, methoxyl, acetate, vinyl groups and trisubstituted benzene ring. 1 on ozonolysis afforded 2-hydroxy-anisaldehyde (2), m.p. 40–41° (lit.³ 40–42° synthetic, m.m.p. and co-tlc), the formation of which confirmed the presence of a benzene ring with the side-chain –CH=CHCOCH₃ having an *ortho*-hydroxy group and a *para*-methoxy group as therein in 1. This got further support from its ¹H nmr spectrum which displayed three separate singlets for a hydroxyl, a methoxyl and an acetate protons, an *ortho*-coupled doublet for H-6 and a *meta*-coupled doublet for H-3, a double doublet for H-5 and two doublets for vinylic protons (J 9.00 Hz). The structure 1 was further confirmed by its ¹³C nmr and mass spectral data.

Compound 3 responded positive reaction to glycoside and gave a fluorescence under uv light indicative for a coumarin glycoside^{4,5}. The ir spectrum of 3 showed principal absorptions for hydroxyl, coumarin lactone, aromatic ring, furan

ring and glycoside. On acetylation it afforded a tetraacetate (4), the ¹H nmr spectrum of which displayed four separate methyl singlets for four acetate groups, a 6H multiplet for sugar protons along with a 1H doublet for anomeric sugar proton, two separate doublets for coumarin lactone ring protons and a singlet for aromatic proton. The above evidences clearly supported that compound 3 is a furanocoumarin glycoside. The acid hydrolysis⁴ of 3 afforded an aglycone (5) and D-glucose (co-pc). The aglycone (5) on methylation afforded the xanthotoxin (6) confirmed by its m.p. (lit.⁶ 144°, ¹H nmr), m.m.p. and co-tlc examinations (isolated from *Limonia acidissima*). Obviously D-glucose must be attached at C-8 in 3. Periodate oxidation⁴ of 3 confirmed D-glucose in pyranose form. The almond enzymatic hydrolysis⁴ of 3 afforded 5 (m.p., m.m.p. and co-tlc, isolated from the demethylated product of 6 from *L. acidissima*) and D-glucose (co-pc) confirming β -linkage between 5 and D-glucose. Thus the structure 3 as xanthotoxol-8-O- β -D-glucopyranoside was assigned to the new furanocoumarin glycoside which was also in complete conformity with ¹³C nmr spectrum of 4.

Experimental

M.ps. were taken on a Toshniwal melting point apparatus and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 157 spectrophotometer, ¹H nmr spectra (DMSO-d₆, 220 MHz for ¹

and CDCl_3 , 90 MHz for 4) on a FT instrument using TMS as an internal standard, ^{13}C nmr spectra ($(\text{CD}_3)_2\text{SO}$ at 90.56 MHz for 1 and in $\text{DMSO}-d_6$ for 4) on a spectrometer, electronic spectra (EtOH) on a Hitachi 320 spectrophotometer and mass spectra on a Jeol JMS-D-300 instrument fitted with direct inlet system operating at 70 eV.

Extraction : Air-dried and powdered heartwood of *A. marmelos* (5 kg; procured from United Chemicals and Allied Products, India) was extracted with hot EtOH for 30 days (using fresh EtOH thrice). From EtOH extract (20 dm³), ethanol was removed under reduced pressure to get a viscous mass which was then successively refluxed with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) and benzene. The petroleum ether extract was concentrated and chromatographed in a column of neutral Al_2O_3 . Hexane-petroleum ether (1 : 1, v/v) eluates afforded β -sitosterol⁷ (800 mg, m.p. 134–35°, m.m.p. and co-tlc). The benzene fraction was concentrated and passed through a column of neutral Al_2O_3 , eluated successively with petroleum ether-benzene (8 : 2, v/v), benzene and benzene-chloroform (6 : 4, v/v) to give lupeol⁸ (800 mg, m.p. 212–14°, m.m.p. and co-tlc), compound 1 as colourless crystalline compound (900 mg) and compound 3 as colourless plates (1.20 g) respectively.

Characterisation of compound 1 : It had m.p. 210–11° (Found : C, 63.40; H, 5.73. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_4$ calcd. for : C, 63.46; H, 5.76%); ν_{max} 3 100 (OH), 2 870 (C–Me), 1 760 (vinyl ester carbonyl), 1 600 (trisubstituted benzene ring), 1 460 and 820 (–CH=CH–), 1 180 (OMe), 1 300, 1 280, 1 200, 1 120, 1 020, 950 and 740 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ 11.00 (1H, s, 2-OH), 7.60 (1H, dd, J 3.00 and 8.00 Hz, H-5), 7.30 (1H, d, J 8.00 Hz, H-6), 6.50 (1H, d, J 3.00 Hz, H-3), 6.35 and 6.25 (2H, d, J 9.00 Hz, –CH=CH–), 3.35 (3H, s, 4-OCH₃) and 2.20 (3H, s, OCOCH₃); ^{13}C nmr 20.0 (OCOCH₃), 55.0 (OCH₃), 109.0 (C- α), 112.0 (C-3), 114.0 (C-5), 123.0 (C-6), 128.0 (C-1), 137.0 (C- β), 141.0 (C-4), 143.0 (C-2) and 160.0 (ester C=O); m/z 208 (M^+), 193, 178, 177, 165, 164 and 149.

Acetylation of 1 : Compound 1 (100 mg) was acylated with Ac_2O (5 ml) and $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{N}$ (5 ml) under reflux condition for 5 h, then cooled and poured into water (100 ml) at 0°. The product was crystallised from CHCl_3 -MeOH mixture as colourless needles, m.p. 190–92° (Found : C, 62.35; H, 5.57. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_5$ calcd. for : C, 62.40; H, 5.60%); ^1H nmr δ 7.60 (1H, dd, J 3.00 and 8.50 Hz, H-5), 7.35 (1H, d, J 8.00 Hz, H-6), 6.50 (1H, d, J 3.00 Hz, H-3), 6.30 and 6.25 (2H, d, J 9.0 Hz, –CH=CH–), 3.35 (3H, s, 4-OCH₃), 2.20 (OCOCH₃) and 2.10 (OCOCH₃).

Ozonolysis of 1 : Compound 1 (100 mg) in glacial acetic acid (10 ml) was ozonised for 2 h at an ozone concentration of about 2%. The product was treated with distilled water (20 ml) and kept at room temperature. The resulting solid was crystallised from ether as colourless crystals (2), m.p.

40–41°, identical with 2-hydroxyanisaldehyde (synthetic).

Characterisation of compound 3 : It recorded m.p. 219–20° (Found : C, 56.12; H, 4.30. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_9$ calcd. for : C, 56.04; H, 4.39%); ν_{max} 3 320–3 300 (OH), 1 710 and 1 630 (coumarin lactone), 1 570 (aromatic ring), 1 150, 1 400, 1 360, 1 270, 955 (coumarin skeleton), 890 (furan ring) and 825 cm^{-1} (glycoside).

Acetylation of 3 : Compound 3 (100 mg) was acetylated similarly as 1, and the product was crystallised from CHCl_3 -EtOAc mixture as buff coloured amorphous solid (4), m.p. 122–23°d; ^1H nmr δ 1.95, 2.00, 2.10 and 2.20 (each 3H, s, 4-OCOCH₃), 3.70–4.50 (6H, m, sugar-H), 4.70 (1H, d, J 7.60 Hz, anomeric sugar-H), 6.30 (1H, d, J 9.50 Hz, H-3), 6.70 (1H, d, J 2.50 Hz, furan H-3), 7.45 (1H, s, H-5), 7.60 (1H, d, J 2.50 Hz, furan H-2) and 7.90 (1H, d, J 9.50 Hz, H-4); ^{13}C nmr δ 20.50 (4-OCOCH₃), 62.00 (C-6'), 64.50 (C-4'), 67.50 (C-3' and C-5'), 68.50 (C-2'), 101.00 (C-1'), 112.50 (furan C-3), 115.50 (C-5), 116.00 (C-3), 117.00 (C-10), 126.50 (C-6), 129.50 (C-8), 144.50 (C-9), 145.50 (C-4), 147.50 (C-7), 148.00 (furan C-2), 159.00 (C-2) and 169.00, 169.40, 170.00, 170.50 (4-OCOCH₃).

Acid hydrolysis of 3 : Compound 3 (800 mg) was hydrolysed with 7% H_2SO_4 (40 ml) by refluxing for 5 h. The resulting solid was washed with distilled water to afford aglycone 5 (500 mg) and D-glucose.

Aglycone 5 : It recorded m.p. 249–50° (Found : C, 65.40; H, 3.07. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_8\text{O}_4$ calcd. for : C, 65.34; H, 2.97%); λ_{max} (log ϵ) 220 (4.45), 243 (4.40), 250 (4.42), 258 (4.22) and 300 nm (4.14); ν_{max} 3 300–3 280 (OH), 1 700 and 1 625 (coumarin lactone), 1 580 (aromatic ring), 1 400, 1 360, 1 275, 1 150 and 950 (coumarin skeleton) and 880 cm^{-1} (furan ring); ^1H nmr δ 6.35 (1H, d, J 9.50 Hz, H-3), 6.80 (1H, d, J 2.50 Hz, furan H-3), 7.40 (1H, s, H-5), 7.65 (1H, d, J 2.50 Hz, furan H-2), 7.70 (1H, d, J 9.50 Hz, H-4) and 11.00 (1H, s, 8-OH); m/z 202 (M^+), 201, 173, 145, 117 and 89.

Methylation of 5 : The aglycone (5; 100 mg) was refluxed with Me_2SO_4 (5 ml) and K_2CO_3 (2 g) in dry acetone (15 ml) for 8 h, then cooled and filtered. The solid so obtained was washed with distilled water and crystallised from ether-ethyl acetate mixture as colourless needles (6; 20 mg) m.p. 143–44°, corresponding to that of xanthotoxin (literature⁶, elemental analysis and ^1H nmr).

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